

FRESH CRATER SPECTRA BASED CHARACTERIZATION OF MINERALOGICAL VARIABILITY IN SERENITATIS & TRANQUILLITATIS REGION. S. Adak and D. Dhingra, Department of Earth Sciences, Indian Institute of Technology Kanpur, Uttar Pradesh, 2028016, India (somnath22@iitk.ac.in, ddhingra@iitk.ac.in)

Introduction: Basalts cover 17% of the lunar surface, and represent layered volcanic flows of varying age, composition and thickness [1]. In regional geologic maps, these flows are commonly treated as laterally homogeneous in composition and classified as discrete mare units [2]. However, systematic compositional stratigraphy of these basaltic units remains poorly constrained. Fresh impact craters expose relatively unweathered subsurface materials, enabling investigation of mineralogical variability within mapped mare units.

This study investigates the mineralogical variability within selected mare units by analyzing reflectance spectra from fresh craters, with strong absorption bands. Using hyperspectral data from the Chandrayaan-1 Moon Mineralogy Mapper (M³), we analyze the crater population within mare units, using titanium abundance as a proxy.

Scientific Motivation: Previous spectral studies of lunar mare basalts have primarily relied on average spectral properties of mare units, derived from datasets with limited spectral and spatial resolution. But such regional analysis may mask mineralogical variability occurring at local scale within individual mare units. Spectra from fresh crater ejecta reveal localised sampling of mare materials and can show compositional variation that are not evident in unit-scale averages. Additionally, variations in spectral characteristics among craters of different sizes may reveal excavation of basalt layers of different mineralogies, giving clues about the near-surface stratigraphy of mare flows [3].

Study Area: Our study focuses on selected mare

Figure 1: Map of WAC-derived TiO₂ abundance + detected craters + Hiesinger mare units for Mare Serenitatis and Mare Tranquillitatis region. (inset: lunar nearside & our study area)

units in Mare Serenitatis and Mare Tranquillitatis region, representing basalt flows of different composition (emplacement ages) (Figure 1).

Data and Methodology: M³ global mode data covering the 0.46-3.0 μm range (85 bands) at 20-40 nm spectral resolution and 140-280 m/pixel spatial resolution were used to extract reflectance spectra of fresh crater ejecta materials [4]. The level-2 reflectance data are photometrically and thermally corrected, but minor residual thermal effects may remain at longer wavelengths [5, 6].

A crater catalogue was first generated using the Automatic Crater Detection (ACD) tool applied to Lunar Reconnaissance Orbiter – Wide Angle Camera (LRO-WAC) mosaics [7]. The detected craters were spatially assigned to Hiesinger Mare Units and grouped into different diameter bins (0.7-1.5 km, 1.5-3.5 km, >3.5 km) representing different excavation depth. M³ reflectance data were then extracted for each identified crater. Band ratio criteria were applied to filter out mature craters and retain spectra showing relatively freshly excavated materials with strong mafic absorption bands.

Adaptive linear continuum removal was applied on extracted spectra to isolate diagnostic absorption features associated with mafic minerals. Spectral parameterization techniques were used to characterize band properties such as band minima positions, band asymmetry, etc. These parameters were used to examine spectral variability within and across mare units.

Result: Reflectance spectra from fresh crater ejecta shows systematic albedo and spectral differ-

Figure 2: Mean fresh crater reflectance spectra of Mare Tranquillitatis vs Mare Serenitatis.

ence between mare regions with varying TiO_2 abundances (Figure 2). High Ti basalts in Mare Tranquillitatis show lower reflectance and weaker ferrous absorption as compared to Mare Serenitatis basalts, consistent with M^3 observation reported by [8]. Our crater based analysis independently confirm the regional fresh crater spectra trends of [8].

Within individual mare units, average spectra from individual craters show noticeable variability in overall albedo, spectral slope and strength of mafic bands (Figure 3).

Figure 3: Intra-unit comparison: All craters' spectra and their mean

Crater diameter binned mean spectra show systematic differences with crater size, expressed as differences in band depth and continuum slope, suggesting differences in the spectral properties of materials excavated from different depths and the degree of vertical mixing of basalt layers (Figure 4).

Figure 4: Diameter-binned mean spectra showing depth dependent trends within mare units.

Discussion: The observed intra-unit spectral variability suggests that mapped mare units may contain greater compositional diversity than previously inferred from regional geologic maps. Variations in spectral properties among craters of different sizes may help characterize mare basalt compositional layering thereby providing better constraints on the composition and its variability in a mare unit or region.

Summary: Analysis of M^3 spectra from fresh crater ejecta shows spectral differences between mare regions of different TiO_2 abundances, consistent with earlier M^3 studies of high-titanium basalts. Within individual mare units, spectra from different craters vary in albedo, mafic band strength, and continuum slope, indicating local variability in the excavated material. Changes in spectra with crater size suggest possible layering within mare basalt flows.

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